

VEIN TREATMENTS: ARE SURGICAL PROCEDURES EFFECTIVE?

When people have varicose or spider veins causing them irritation and pain in the legs, they need **vein treatment near me**. Before getting a **vein treatment in new jersey**, consult a **vein doctor Paramus** to determine the correct and accurate method for you. It is always mandatory to learn and understand various types of [vein treatments New Jersey](#) before getting them.

What are Varicose or Spider veins?

Varicose and spider veins are enlarged blood vessels that can most commonly be found on the patient's legs. Sometimes painful or itchy, they can form ulcers and scabs if you scratch them excessively. They have valves that work to regulate the overall flow of blood. Sometimes these valves can become damaged or missing, and the vein subsequently gets filled with backed-up blood. The bulging purplish, blue, or red spidery patterns on your legs are actually clogged capillaries where blood is unable to pass through.

Symptoms of Abnormal Leg Veins:

- Inflammation and discomfort in the legs or ankles.
- Certain spots on your legs are disturbing, painful, or warm to the touch.
- Feeling of tightness in the calves.
- A dull, tired, or uneasy feeling in your leg.
- Pain when walking or soon after stopping.
- Skin color variations, redness, or flaky skin.
- Wounds or ulcers.
- Foot spasms.

Surgical Vein Treatments:

Ambulatory phlebectomy:

The treatment usually involves vein removal, which has become a fairly common procedure since so many people suffer from the condition of varicose and/or spider. A small incision right over the vein in question allows the **vein doctor near Paramus** to remove the damaged one from your body while you slumber peacefully under anesthesia. This procedure is called ambulatory phlebectomy.

Vein stripping:

There's also the option to undergo surgical vein stripping, which involves a small incision near the groin and one near the ankle so that a thin tube may be passed through to remove the

damaged ones by a **vein specialist near me**. Surgical vein stripping is an outpatient procedure and this treatment is far less invasive than a traditional removal.

You may be considering this [vein treatment Clifton](#) simply for cosmetic reasons so that you can feel good showing off your legs again or go without pants or pantyhose. Or you may have a health condition caused by your varicose or spider veins, such as circulatory problems, leg pain, or irritation. Whatever the reason for undergoing this **vein treatment NJ**, you can rest assured that the procedure is very safe and that a skilled surgeon will walk you through the whole thing.

Side Effects of Surgical Vein Treatment:

As with any surgical **vein treatment near my woodland park**, there are some risks involved. Bleeding, infection, poor healing or scarring, nerve damage, change in sensation, discoloration and other complications may occur but in most cases will not. The potential benefits may outweigh the risks, but that is something you should discuss with a qualified cosmetic surgeon who has experience performing vein treatment procedures. If you do decide to have the surgery, you are likely to come through feeling better about yourself than ever before.

If you feel any serious discomfort consult a **vein doctor near me**.